

The Impact of Knowledge Management on The Performance of Employees: The Case of Small Medium Enterprises

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Abstract

Technology is the resource of the new economy, and the center of technology administration, the essence of corporate organizations. It was used as a method for generating sustainable economic gains and higher performance from the 1990s. It has now become a key asset to maintain profitable corporate advantages and a catalyst for sustained progress and innovation. Each corporation aims to expand and develop whether it is a small business or a large company so that the owners can return on their investment. This objective can be achieved by sustainably superior corporate efficiency. Several variables will affect the current economy's operational success, but information management is becoming more relevant. This paper is intended to summarize knowledge management, emphasizing the importance of this practice area and, on the other hand, presenting some case studies on how knowledge management from various industries is applied. Therefore, after analyzing many case studies where knowledge management is applied, we will explore the concept that knowledge management has significant consequences for an organisation's efficiency. We will continue

by emphasizing organisations' general view, their current economy, the information management framework, and how it can be used in organizations. This is accompanied by an overview of information management instances applied and their effect on overall performance. Ultimately, our statement indicates that knowledge management has a positive impact on business efficiency.

Keywords: Knowledge Management; Organizational Performance; SMEs; Knowledge Economy.

Introduction and preliminary literature review

The theory of knowledge management (KM) has been developing since 1991 as a management and information system methodology. KM has become one of the most common and new technology for management. The correlation between awareness and organization overall performance is one of the most discussed fields of KM. There is past relationship research, but there is still a lack of understanding and agreement. The disparity between knowledge bases and the organization's willingness to use and grow expertise [1] is crucial for business strategy and success. The groundbreaking academic discussion focused mainly on the information management principle [2], [30]. KM represents the company's policies and activities to improve efficiency and effectiveness in handling organizational information capital, to unlock its intellectual potential [3], [4], [5].

Generalization of organizations

As a community associated with specific tasks to meet clear goals, Bittner [16] identifies an organisation [6]. This ensures it is important that all people involved in an organization, through individual or group schooling, recognize the goals, and continually improve their skills to participate actively in the collaborative effort required to achieve them. This facilitates the enterprise's successful operation, as the secret to improving operational success and promoting management approaches is organizational and human capacities [13].

Understanding the current economy

In addition to organizational skills and staff, the enterprise's environment is also important to understand. The companies currently work in what is also considered "the information economy," which is a market in the technology-intensive operations of manufacturing and distribution [7]. These knowledge-intensive practices could be found by using "ShareNet" [8] and Microsoft in several major organizations, such as Siemens, through the use of "Sharepoint." Powell and Snellman have demonstrated that technological and scientific developments in this

knowledge economy can be increased while also becoming much more redundant. This illustrates how complex organization-based assisted technology is and the value of corporate development, which is the ongoing manifestation of what has been experienced in the organization's processes [25]. Organizational development relies on research; this essentially requires the creation and effective application of new knowledge [23].

The need to manage knowledge

Senior companies are more focused during the knowledge-based economy on their knowledge-based capital to sustain and cope with the transition [18], [24], [26], [37]. Consequently, the application of Knowledge Management (KM) is becoming a primary tool for optimizing various organizations' operational efficiency. According to resource-based views (RBV) and knowledge-based views (KBVs), knowledge is a vital tool for organizations' sustainability, stability, and growth. Since 1990, companies have been closely linked to information management [21], [24], [28], [30], [9]. Organisations became competitive in the early 1990s.

With a significantly shorter capital [10] and increasingly competitive economies, the current system is very complex and a growing innovation pace. The strength of four forces that drive the need to handle knowledge in this current economy was Beccera-Fernandez and Sabherwal, namely [15]: the "growing domain sophistication" which means that it becomes increasingly complex to achieve a particular business task; the "accelerated market volatility" which implies a substantial increase in the rate of changing market patterns about this

Basing on the above four powers, competition's competitive nature puts pressure on companies, which could risk their business knowledge to minimize the workforce. Staff cutback generates a demand that silent information (informal awareness, intelligent persons) be supplemented by explicit knowledge (formal, processed knowledge). The bulk of organizational knowledge is in the form of informal knowledge. The lack of corporate expertise always goes hand in hand with early retirement, expanded employee productivity, and necessary organizational strategic direction changes. To make the problem worse, the time available for observing and acquiring knowledge has deteriorated constantly in this financial era. Any events involving one of the factors mentioned will thus contribute to a collapse in organizational efficiency. To achieve and retain the required anticipated corporate performance level and gain a competitive advantage, the need to handle operational information efficiently [27].

Knowledge Management and its relevance to the knowledge economy

Seeing that companies today work within a knowledge economy and are based on wisdom-intensive practices for sustained productivity, it is becoming ever more important to handle expertise effectively. Information is now treated as an (explicit) useful item for information

embedded goods and highly exposed (tacit) by highly mobile workers. Therefore, the creation and distribution of such products are important factors in sustainable competitiveness [20]. Knowledge is seen as an internal power in this competitive environment [11] and is the real asset of organizations in the light of their survival. Without awareness, it is very difficult for organizations to respond effectively to ever-changing market demands to remain competitive, and the principles of information management are therefore becoming important for any company, be it big, medium, or tiny, even if their management methodology may be specific [33].

The use of accessible information tools through translating human knowledge (tacit) into organizational knowledge (explicitly) can be described as knowledge management [32]. More precisely, as a structured mechanism in which information can be gained, produced, developed, processed, distributed, and exchanged, and used to increase employees [25]. As Dalkir [20] has emphasized, bringing workers together for the best through silos breaks down, promotes new cooperation, and is individually and collectively more successful. It encourages workers to continue to increase their expertise, making them more efficient and effective, and contribute more. This enables creating a powerful corporate history to further the challenges of established and disseminated best practices across the enterprise, provide more room for creativity by the partnership, and produce better knowledge-based products and services [31].

Knowledge management enables people, systems, and technological development to build expectations between intangible and measurable assets in both organisations. This allows new opportunities in industry to be found and established through the use of information obtained by the specialist, quick and easy access to the necessary knowledge in all situations at any moment, that is to say, to ensure that the necessary knowledge is always in the right place in the correct manner, at the right time and to make the execution more responsive and more successful. It also leads to further exchanging information with different players, which can greatly strengthen existing or new partnerships. For example, better customer interactions will typically lead to better customer loyalty and a better public organization. This helps improve workplace engagement, promotes the continuous growth of people's capacity through individual or group learning, and fosters corporate learning to boost productivity and resources and the overall impact on the organizational success [12].

Knowledge Management (KM) has a key source of sustainable competitive advantage for businesses, and in the last two decades, it has had a more positive impact on company results. The research has indicated that awareness and resources have been generated and identified by persons with artistic and cognitive ability. The same can be said, on the other side, of those companies that use their resources efficiently. Nevertheless, there is no systematic distribution of information and resources among people in organizations. The ability to find and leverage

opportunities depends on individuals' skills and expertise and the ability to manage and benefit from the invalid source listed forms. One of KM's anticipated benefits is the increase in revenue and overall performance. Sales growth in its association with KM experience is the common term used for calculating the efficiency and effectiveness of business. Nevertheless, several previous studies suggest that the important sales performance indicator is market share and development Invalid source. Jayasingam et al. [22] reported a significant impact on KM adoption's operational and sales efficiency and the activities [34].

The Knowledge Management life cycle

The value of information management to companies is evident, and their commitment to providing services and goods is the path to progress in corporate performance [36]. Information management helps companies use their information tools to prepare better, develop, organize, and inspire workers. Another significant by-product of information management is the convergence of individual persons, systems, and technologies as a single unit [25]. Organizations always need to turn tacit knowledge into explicit knowledge, enabling re-using expertise to enhance processes. The process of knowledge management provides a roadmap for the successful application of knowledge management within organizations and the person responsible for obeying this guide closely [35].

KM life cycle ends with building awareness in which people create new ways of making the business process efficient and effective in businesses. As mentioned by Nonaka [30], the development of information comes mainly from organizational workers by community communication, interactions, skills, and attitudes. The development of information takes two forms: implicit awareness and explicit knowledge. Explicit information may be extracted from various already codified and preserved sources, including books, journals, records, newspapers, and educational material [19]. In this process, an information-based management structure is established, and the basis of expertise is generated both internally and from other sources.

The information gained would be collected using various methods for collecting, such as interviews, questionnaires, assessments, blackboards, findings on-site, and brainstorming, to name a few [14]. It is then codified to alter, coordinate, and process captured information, as Newman and W [29] have described. Conrad would allow institutions to store codified information and incorporate codified knowledge in their everyday work. After the codified information has been preserved, it must be transmitted. Once organizations learn some material, expertise should be exchanged with other employees if the knowledge-based system continues to be improved or departmental issues addressed further. Newman and W. [29] According to Conrad, the exchange of information is an important component of corporate progress. The quicker it is shared, the longer the response period is, and thus, the greater the organizational efficiency. Because of the driving forces early mentioned, it is also critical for the company to

see their information inventories often to ensure their capacity to respond appropriately, considering that operational objectives and consumer needs will shift. The Knowledge Review is, therefore, a critical step since it helps organizations, using knowledge exercise, to review their information, assess their intellectual assets, and recognize their knowledge gaps.

Problems/Issues with Knowledge Management

Today in many organizations, there are many issues regarding information management, and the shortage of professional human resources is a major concern. The administration of information relies more on individuals to gather more tacit knowledge and transform it into explicit knowledge. Knowledge is the true power and resources of businesses and is seen as a key source to gain competitive advantages in today's changing world. Another challenge is that departmental staff sometimes don't want to handle complex processes. Another problem facing many organizations today is the lack of ties between Departmental Systems across various departments. Departmental networks need to be able to interact because individual sessions take time and usually interrupt procedures. Interaction between the departmental structure will alleviate these issues if they are not eliminated, thereby significantly improving inter-departmental decision making. The lack of documentation of some business processes in divisions can also contribute to these issues, and in some areas of expertise within departments, there is a lack of knowledge. The worse issue is probably that many companies, particularly small and medium-sized enterprising [17], do not know the definition of information management. All such considerations may contribute to variability in organizational decision-making efficiency.

Exploring some knowledge management case studies

There are now several issues with information management in many organizations, and the lack of professional human resources is a big problem. To order for practitioners to collect tacit knowledge and turn it into explicit knowledge, information processing depends on individuals. Knowledge is the real power and capital of companies and is seen in today's changing world as a major source for competitive advantages. The departmental workers are sometimes not prepared to deal with complex procedures, another obstacle. The absence of connections between Departmental Teams in various departments is another problem facing several organizations today. Departmental networks must be able to interact because it takes time for individual sessions to disrupt procedures. When inter-ministerial decision-making is not eliminated, the relationship with the departmental system should mitigate those issues. The lack of documentation for some branch business processes can also add to these issues, and there is a lack of knowledge in certain areas of expertise within organizations. The worse question is likely that many businesses, particularly small and medium-sized organizations, do not know the

definition of information management [17]. These factors may lead to variations in the performance of an organization's decisions.

Case Study: The Siemens ICN Knowledge Management Challenge: ICN/ICM ShareNet (KnowledgeBoard, 2002) – Telecom Industry

Need for knowledge management

In the mid-1990s, a massive change was witnessed in the market environment, which led to new entrants joining the telecommunications industry and a surge in competition because of new technological advances. A better service strategy had to overcome Siemens' single goods market style. Siemens developed a program for information management to change further the global network of knowledge sharing called ShareNet. Siemens has been able to bring together its front-line staff, who are better informed about market trends, to obtain the market knowledge needed.

Leveraging local innovations globally

Because Siemens is a global organization, it has several foreign experts. ShareNet helps the expert's network and share and improve their knowledge to provide better customer solutions. This could identify and leverage local technologies worldwide. Siemens' multinational existence made ShareNet outside of the time zone, contributing to a much smoother response to questions.

Getting members to contribute knowledge

It would be a task for Siemens to add information to all members by offering reader/user status and editors status. This concept was not focused on a specific and special' source of knowledge,' but rather on the reality that all participants belong individually to an easy-to-use global environment and have a little red tape and' barriers to entry' of the collective knowledge of the world community. Wherever participants are, they will apply their expertise about their roles by submitting Web-based project questionnaires.

Providing universal access to knowledge

The use of universal access to sales, commercialization, and business expertise will boost trust and a chance to earn winning ventures by using previous approaches, creative pricing strategies, and success stories for customers. Every information repeated together with a personalized input worth ranking would also be given with reviews and opinions. Because ShareNet worked as a decentralized entity embedded in daily work, assistance had to be given for its successful use. At least one ShareNet Assistance Manager had been allocated to each local firm.

Incentive systems to encourage knowledge sharing

Siemens has also introduced reward programs to allow participants to share their knowledge to improve the chance of success of the ShareNet program. Giving and donating –since other people helped solve your problem, it is only normal that you return the favor. It requires reward schemes. The customized feature allows ShareNet to identify important members and increase their likelihood of being noticed and compensated by the multinational organization. Bonus points for ShareNets Members-valuable contributions will contribute to sharing bonus points for prizes related to user information growth.

The benefits of the ShareNet initiative

The benefits of the ShareNet initiative were measured for both the organization and for the individual, and the main advantages Siemens derived from it were:

- It has provided real-life experience knowledge business targets with well-tested customer solutions that can be escalated to similar circumstances.
- Save time to develop value-added services or products, build better customer relations, and introduce new products and services.
- Increasing client engagement development cycles and promote more staff interaction by enhancing their commitment exposure.
- Saving consulting fees is important to provide details and analyzes studies from professional experts on a global basis wherever feasible.
- The exposure of creative consumer products for future reuse to create new income streams for all stakeholders elsewhere.
- Quick understanding and response to market changes due to the networked front liners employees from different locations contribute to and enhance their capabilities to quickly appreciate any changes, market trends, technology developments, and customer requirements.

HSBC (Banking and Finance Industry)

The need for knowledge management

HSBC has decided to incorporate information management to advance its well-functioning business units as a significant banking and financial services organization. The size and strength offered a good chance of creating a large knowledge base. The global capabilities of its workers will potentially lead to this; this move could also aid.

The approach to knowledge management

If required, information auditing was carried out, action plans were developed, and adequate knowledge management resources were put in place. A specialized team was responsible for the knowledge management initiative. The workplace information will continuously be collected, codified, communicated, and used throughout the enterprise via knowledge management tools. It means that the history of corporate expertise has always been up to date, demonstrating the importance of senior staff who are the main contributors to information and simplifying newcomers' absorption and learning.

The challenges in implementing the knowledge management initiative

When predicted, administrators in large organizations continue to be overwhelmed, and executives often found that they could not successfully manage the tools and techniques for information management on time. Most of their short-term (generally shorter than a year), whereas proposals for information improvement may take much longer than a year. This would not adhere to their existing set of objectives and deliverables, which in effect would harm their annual performance assessment.

It generated some reluctance to accept information management programs freely and pursue them. Foreign managers who were not trained in information management did not understand it well, although much effort was needed to clarify what it was before it got underway. Besides, several other restraining variables were also found. The problem was alleviated, and understanding was increased by the use of the information management brochure. The long cycle of introduction and implementation-results is a sluggish return on investment in information management programs. The structure and processes of broad corporate structures that occur are well known and very valued.

The benefits of the initiative

The benefit of the program has been calculated for both the company and the client and HSBC's key advantages: an improved corporate memory that increases the interest of senior employees while at the same time reducing the learning curve. Better awareness of market trends and the direct relationship between customers and employees. Enhanced ability for information processing and knowledge sharing. Proper sorting, screening, and detecting inaccurate and outdated information may easily be done, saving time as strategies are being built with client agreements, increasing employee and consumer awareness, and better customer service.

- Service reliability and quality (cost and personnel reduction, sales growth, and profitability) improved.
- Better knowledge of consumers has helped improve targeted marketing and promotions when new target audiences are available.
- Customer loyalty is enhanced with a powerful interactive culture. It also helped to achieve good processes for sharing knowledge and improve customer services systematically.

The WISECARE project (<http://wisecare.nurs.uoa.gr/>) – Service Industry

The need for knowledge management and the approach

To strengthen cancer infirming activities through various European nations, the WISECARE project was an awareness sharing program. Appropriate tools have implemented aid to the comprehensive use of electronic patient records in professional nursing data management information. The platform has made them available to all participating countries and has contributed to a strong knowledge base on best nursing care practices. Each participating organization could easily make observations and success assessments against other participating organizations' best practices, and automatically steps needed for change could be taken automatically.

The benefits of the WISECARE project

Because appropriate knowledge management systems have enabled WISECARE, it naturally has the benefits of information technology: increased performance, error prevention, improved communication, and simple documentation. In addition to IT's advantages, the nursing organization has been the key benefit of unparalleled creative ways of information-sharing that include transmission, the substitution of organizational awareness, and the change from deductive knowledge to inductive knowledge. New methods for a deeper use of health records were also established to enhance clinical option

Discussion

It is shown that information improvement programs in organizations, which can be extended to similar conditions, can provide real-life business organization priorities through well-testing consumer approaches. This can save businesses substantial production time for value-added services or products and gives them more time to develop better relationships with customers and work on new products or services. It can also reduce the development cycle of consumer engagement and encourage greater worker commitment by growing the exposure and enhancing their inputs' customer service. Rich consumer experience and an emphasis on time-saving value

creation will allow a company to develop innovative solutions that companies can use at all locations. This can build new revenue streams by itself. In companies employing contractors, information management programs can be used to reduce consulting expenses. It is possible to access all eligible personnel through knowledge and review of potential consultants' results. Compared to the reviews of contractors, information management may give companies similar benefits by using their personnel. It can lead to the networking of its frontline staff from different locations to improve their ability to quickly identify shifts to market trends, technological developments, and customer needs and ensuring that appropriate answers are instant.

Conclusion

In the sense of information management programs, too, corporate awareness would be kept up to date. This mechanism will hold senior officials still highly respected by organizations while growing the new entrants' learning curve, as senior employees usually give improved information. Knowledge management tools provide the necessary resources for the management and professional staff to process information in their corporate memory and conduct knowledge sharing. They will enable me to recognize inaccurate and outdated expertise and process the content. Therefore, through reducing costs and employees, increasing marketing knowledge and productivity, and enhancing coherent decision making, organizations would become more efficient and effective.

Future Recommendations

Thus, we can strongly argue that the advantages of correctly applied knowledge management programs within the organizations, whether large organizations or SMEs, will positively impact corporate success as their approach to knowledge management can vary. Nonetheless, it must be properly implemented, as previously mentioned. All senior managers should be aware of the concept to provide adequate support, ensuring that it is applied promptly and completes the period of expected results, make adequate investments accessible for their support technology and establish good opportunities for knowledge-sharing.

The knowledge management framework fits any organization which carries out knowledge-intensive activities naturally. And because it has been shown that wisdom-intensive practices are the path forward in today's knowledge economy, the idea of knowledge management is an essential aspect of any organization that works in that expertise-based economy. Therefore, it is important to efficiently and effectively handle the enterprise's information assets and capital and incorporate knowledge management practices in enterprises to consistently function, gain, and maintain a competitive advantage within such an economy.

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